

Title	Aligning TRE Assurance Frameworks in the UK: A SATRE-Based Control Alignment Approach
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Executive Summary

Trusted Research Environments (TRE)'s are essential for secure, ethical research using sensitive health and administrative data. However, the UK assurance landscape is fragmented: TRE operators must navigate multiple frameworks, including ISO/IEC 27001, the Digital Economy Act 2017 (DEA), the NHS Data Security and Protection Toolkit (DSPT), Cyber Essentials, and the SDE Self-Assessment Framework.

This paper is intended for TRE operators, data controllers, and organisations working to evidence robust governance within a TRE. Because different data controllers adopt different assurance frameworks based on their risk appetite and requirements, TREs face inconsistent expectations of what "good governance" entails. By positioning SATRE as the reference framework, this work offers a way to map and demonstrate equivalence across the major UK frameworks, supporting clear, consistent, and transparent governance claims.

This fragmentation creates duplication, inefficiency, and inconsistent interpretation of compliance. Data controllers face uncertainty in recognising equivalence across frameworks, and TREs must repeatedly demonstrate the same controls. This not only delays audit readiness but also limits collaboration as organisation cannot rely on or reuse each other's assurance activities.

This paper presents a SATRE-centric control alignment methodology. Using the [Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments \(SATRE\)](#) as the reference framework, controls from major UK assurance frameworks are mapped into a single [Control Alignment Table](#). This approach:

- Provide a roadmap for organisations moving from one accreditation to the next
- Reduces duplication and streamlines assurance by enabling TREs to reuse evidence across frameworks.
- Gives data controllers transparency on equivalence, supporting consistent governance expectations
- Enables federated research by helping TREs interoperate securely across institutions..

By using SATRE-based alignment, TRE operators, data controllers, and assurance bodies can collaborate more efficiently, strengthen trust in TREs, and unlock the full value of data for research and society.

1. Introduction

Trusted Research Environments (TREs), sometimes referred to as Secure Data Environments (SDEs) or Data Safe Havens, are central to the UK's data research ecosystem, providing secure platforms for accessing sensitive datasets while maintaining privacy and public trust.

TRE operators face a fragmented assurance landscape. Multiple frameworks, ISO/IEC 27001, DEA, DSPT, Cyber Essentials, and SDE Self-Assessment, impose overlapping requirements. This complexity leads to:

- Duplicated assurance activities; increasing operational burden.
- Inconsistent expectations; challenging audit readiness.
- Uncertainty for data controllers; who struggle to interpret equivalence across different frameworks which slows down information governance approvals.

To address these challenges, this paper presents a SATRE-centric alignment methodology. By using SATRE, the Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments, as the reference framework, controls from multiple UK frameworks are mapped into a Control Alignment Table. The table helps TRE operators reduce duplication, provides data controllers with a clear view of equivalence, and supports secure, federated collaboration across institutions. Crucially, it also offers organisation a practical roadmap for progressing between assurance frameworks.

2. Background and Context

2.1 Trusted Research Environments in the UK

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) are secure computing environments that enable researchers to analyse sensitive data (e.g. health and administrative data) without exposing the raw data itself. They are designed to deliver security, transparency, and trustworthiness through a combination of technical, organisational, and governance controls.

In practice, these controls are increasingly articulated and assured through the [Five Safes Framework](#), Safe Projects, Safe People, Safe Data, Safe Settings, and Safe Outputs, which provides a coherent, end-to-end model for managing disclosure risk across the research lifecycle. Within TREs, this means ensuring that research purposes are appropriate and publicly defensible (Safe Projects), access is limited to trained and accredited researchers (Safe People), data are minimised and treated to reduce identifiability (Safe Data), analysis takes place within robust secure environments (Safe Settings), and results are checked prior to release (Safe Outputs).

Expectations for TREs are evolving. Beyond strong technical controls, there is growing demand for demonstrable alignment across multiple assurance frameworks, driven by calls from DARE UK for federated architectures, stakeholder demand for mutual recognition of accreditation and HDR UK Alliance principles for trusted, scale-up data linkage, supporting collaboration.

There is a growing ecosystem of TREs across the UK, reflecting different scales, governance model and data types:

[Health Informatics Centre \(HIC\)](#), University of Dundee provides a regional safe haven, ISO27001, for health and care data supporting both local and national research

[SAIL Databank \(Wales\)](#) one of the longest running TRE's in the UK offers population scale linked health and administrative data

[Scottish National Safe Haven](#) is provided by EPCC who operate an environment that hosts multiple independent TRE's each within its own information governance and isolated compute environment.

[DATAMIND TRE \(UK Wide\)](#) focussed on mental health research enabling privacy preserving linkage of health, education and social care datasets

[University of York Data Safe Haven](#) a University hosted TRE supporting secure research across multiple disciplines

[East of England Secure Data Environment \(SDE\)](#) a regional SDE, ISO27001 certified offering a secure and governed analytic workspace for NHS data.

This small sample of real-world TRE's illustrate the breadth of secure infrastructure in the UK from national to regional platforms and highlight the need for consistent governance, transparency and alignment across assurance frameworks.

2.2 Assurance Frameworks

TRE operators engage with multiple assurance frameworks, each with distinct focus areas:

[SATRE](#): community-led TRE-specific framework offering detailed, structured controls tailored to research environments.

[ISO/IEC 27001](#): international standard for information security management.

[Digital Economy Act 2017 \(DEA\)](#): accreditation requirements for organisations processing data held by public authorities under Chapter 5, Part 5 of the DEA (excludes health and social care data held by public authorities with functions relating to providing health or social care) .

[NHS DSPToolkit \(DSPT\)](#): demonstrates compliance with NHS data security and protection requirements.

[SDE Self-Assessment Framework](#): self-evaluation framework for Secure Data Environments.

[Cyber Essentials](#): UK government-backed scheme providing baseline cybersecurity protections.

While these frameworks share some overlapping controls, they differ in scope, granularity, and intended audience. This variation creates duplication, inefficiency, and challenges in recognising equivalence for TRE operators and data controllers.

The frameworks also differ in the resource required to meet and maintain alignment. For example, ISO accreditation requires regular audit by an external, commercial auditor which

approves your accreditation whereas SATRE is a self-assessment process to help guide self-improvement.

3. Methodology

3.1 *Selecting SATRE as the Reference Framework*

SATRE was chosen as the central reference for alignment because it is:

Tailored: designed specifically for TREs.

Granular: detailed enough to support meaningful cross-framework mapping.

Relevant: increasingly adopted within UK TRE initiatives.

Using SATRE as the reference framework provides a common language of assurance for TRE operators and data controllers, enabling clearer interpretation of equivalence across frameworks. Its evolutionary design ensure that it can adapt over time as TRE practices, assurance requirements and frameworks develop.

3.2 *Control Mapping Process*

We approached alignment in three key steps:

Control Identification: extract relevant controls from each framework.

Comparison: map each control to SATRE, categorising as equivalent or gap.

Validation: review mappings with subject matter experts and community stakeholders.

Supporting tools include published framework documentation, internal cross-referencing matrixes, and prior mapping resources where available.

3.3 *Control Alignment Table*

The output of this process is the [Control Alignment Table](#), presenting SATRE controls alongside equivalents in ISO 27001, DEA, DSPT, Cyber Essentials, and the SDE framework. The categories in the table are:

Equivalent: full alignment.

Gap: no clear counterpart.

The table provides TRE operators with a streamlined compliance reference and data controllers with clarity on equivalence, facilitating more efficient assurance, and enabling federated research operations.

4. Benefits and Implications

This section describes the benefits of SATRE-based alignment for TRE operators, data controllers, and standards organisations, and highlights how it enables federated governance reducing duplication, accelerating approvals, and supporting secure, interoperable research across institutions.

Stakeholder Benefits

Stakeholder	Key Benefits	Details / Implications
TRE Operators	Streamlined assurance	Reduces duplication across frameworks; saves time and resources.
	Improved audit readiness	Integrated view of controls makes preparation for audits more efficient.
	Enhanced transparency	Publishing results enables stakeholders to see evidence of compliance.
Data Controllers	Clarity on equivalence	TREs meeting different frameworks can demonstrate comparable assurance.
	Risk-based assurance	Moves beyond reliance on single certifications; supports proportionate oversight.
	Confidence in operations	TREs can interoperate securely and efficiently.
Standards / Accreditation Organisations	Gap identification	Helps identify areas where accrediting TRE capabilities may need improvement.
	Reduced subjectivity	Evaluations become less subjective as statements are interpreted in the context of mapped controls.

Systemic Challenges Addressed by SATRE Alignment

Cause / Challenge	Effect / Impact	SATRE Alignment Solution / Benefit
TREs must repeatedly present evidence to multiple governance boards and data controllers.	Approvals are slowed, costs increase, and agility is limited.	SATRE-based Control Alignment Table enables “trust once, use many times” approvals, reducing duplication and accelerating federated research.
Lack of clarity across multiple frameworks.	Data controllers and standards bodies struggle to recognise equivalence.	Provides a common reference framework, making equivalence transparent and risk-based assurance easier.
Subjective interpretation of compliance statements.	Evaluations vary, leading to inconsistent accreditation and duplicated effort.	Mapping across frameworks contextualises statements, reducing subjectivity and streamlining evaluation.
Fragmented assurance landscape.	TRE operators face inefficiency, repeated audits, and duplicated evidence.	Integrated view of controls reduces duplication, improves audit readiness, and enhances transparency.

6. Limitations

Scope: This work provides guidance only and does not constitute legal or formal accreditation advice.

Framework evolution: As frameworks change, mappings must be regularly reviewed and updated.

One-way mapping: The current mappings were developed with SATRE as the reference framework and do not include reciprocal mapping. As a result, there may be gaps where other frameworks capture requirements useful to SATRE or TREs that are not represented in this version.

Interpretation variability: Application of controls may differ between TREs, introducing subjectivity into equivalence assessments.

7. Potential Future Work

There's still plenty to do to make SATRE alignment even more useful and practical. Here are some areas we see as the next steps:

Formal SATRE Evaluation and Publication: Create a clear, standard process for publishing SATRE evaluations so organisations can share verifiable records of their alignment. This would make compliance more transparent and easier to trust.

Lifecycle Compliance: Move beyond one-off assessments and establish a repeatable cycle—submission, validation, recognition, renewal, and expiry. A structured lifecycle will help TREs keep governance current and consistent.

Automation and Tooling: Build tools that keep mappings up to date automatically, track equivalence across frameworks, and support federated TRE networks at scale. This will save time and reduce manual effort.

Community Practice Sharing: Encourage TREs to share templates, processes, and evidence. The more we pool resources, the less duplication and the more consistent assurance becomes.

Standardisation: Work toward making SATRE a national reference model for equivalence. This won't replace existing frameworks but will give everyone a common language for alignment.

Continuous Improvement: Capture lessons learned from real-world use, what worked, what didn't and feed that back into the methodology. This keeps SATRE practical and relevant.

Framework Convergence: Better mapping could lead to closer alignment between frameworks over time. Full convergence may be a long way off, but even partial harmonisation would simplify governance for everyone.

8. Conclusion

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) operate within a complex and fragmented assurance landscape, requiring alignment with multiple frameworks that differ in scope, emphasis, and assurance mechanisms. As demonstrated throughout this paper, this fragmentation leads to the creation of extra work, slows approvals, and makes it hard for data controllers to see where equivalence exists.

This paper has presented a SATRE-centric control alignment approach, using SATRE as a reference framework to map and compare controls across major UK assurance regimes. The resulting Control Alignment Table provides a practical mechanism for making equivalence explicit, supports reuse of assurance evidence, and improves transparency in governance decisions without requiring replacement or harmonisation of existing frameworks.

By making assurance practices more interpretable and reusable, SATRE-based alignment can reduce duplicated effort, accelerate approvals, and support more efficient cross-institutional collaboration. Over time, improved equivalence mapping may facilitate

partial convergence of assurance frameworks, further simplifying governance while preserving local autonomy.

Call to Action

The next step is collaboration.

TRE Operators should adopt SATRE to streamline their assurance processes and maintain demonstrable compliance with mapped frameworks.

Data Controllers and Governance Boards should work together to formalise recognition of equivalence across frameworks using evidence of compliance as the basis of trust.

TRE Community should develop a SATRE TRE Registry that records compliance, alignment and equivalence would support transparency and interoperability.

TRE Community should continue to share lessons learned to standardise mappings, and explore automation to embed this approach within national assurance processes.

By aligning around SATRE, formalising compliance, and embracing federated governance, the UK can move from fragmented assurance to shared trust enabling secure, efficient, and scalable research that delivers greater public value from data.

Case Study: Health Informatics Centre

When the Health Informatics Centre (HIC) first engaged with the SATRE framework, it represented familiar operational ground. However, expectations were still emerging, and the team, working closely with peers across the Scottish Safe Haven Network (SSHN), approached the initial self-assessment with some caution. HIC published its early submission, acknowledging that it might not yet fully reflect the maturity ultimately expected.

Since then, the publication of the SATRE mapping table has been transformative. It enabled us to revisit our assessment systematically, align evidence more consistently, and clearly demonstrate control coverage. Although our overall score shifted only marginally, the clarity and confidence gained through structured mapping were significant. We can now evidence control fulfilment with greater precision and transparency supported by the internal expertise that has matured during this journey.

For TREs already operating within frameworks such as ISO 27001, the control alignment table is particularly valuable. It accelerates alignment, reduces duplication, and supports coherent control management across standards. HIC has now published its updated SATRE mapping, reinforcing our commitment to transparency.

Why this matters to us: Publishing HIC's SATRE position demonstrates accountability and transparency strengthening trust with stakeholders. Importantly, each research project continues to inform and refine our operational governance, ensuring our TRE evolves in tandem with real-world practice. This iterative approach underscores a core belief at HIC: effective governance is operational, lived, and continuously improved.

In applying SATRE to HIC we identified a need for a data use register which we have since developed. It is publicly available for the benefit of transparency and clarity to the public and our data partners.

Scottish Safe Haven Network: The SSHN which consists of four regional and the national safe haven are ready to publish their peer-reviewed SATRE early next year, a milestone that will formally demonstrate Scotland's alignment with the SATRE framework and provide a clear model of recognised assurance.

Case Study: Health Innovation East

For the East of England Secure Data Environment (SDE), undertaking the SATRE self-assessment was a chance to pause and take stock. Our team approached the exercise as more than a compliance task; it was an opportunity to evaluate how effectively our operational governance and assurance processes were working in practice. SATRE provided a structured way to assess maturity and identify where future development should focus.

Having already aligned with ISO 27001, the Data Security and Protection Toolkit (DSPT), and NHS England's SDE accreditation, we were encouraged to see these strengths reflected in the assessment. Beyond validation, it gave us a clearer view of how evidence is organised and how the relationships between different assurance frameworks can be strengthened to create a more integrated governance model.

The process also highlighted tangible areas for improvement. These include greater automation in configuration and metadata management, development of richer reporting dashboards and training resources, and expansion of technical capability through high-performance computing and enhanced disclosure controls. Collectively, these refinements will improve both efficiency and user experience.

We have published our SATRE outcomes as part of our commitment to accountability and transparency. Engaging with the framework has already deepened our understanding of how assurance models interact in practice and strengthened a culture of continuous improvement. For us, information governance is not a static achievement, but an evolving practice shaped by reflection, collaboration, and ongoing learning.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the wider SATRE project team for their support, constructive feedback, and valuable insights throughout the development of this report. In particular, we are grateful to Simon Li, Tim Machin, Rob Baxter and Antony Chuter for their comments, technical guidance, and engagement in discussions that helped shape this work.